

NAUTILUS

D8.4 Workbook for public workshop

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CHANTIERS
DE L'ATLANTIQUE

CARNIVAL
MARITIME

EPFL

ΘΡΑΚΗΤ ΓΑΡΑΝΤ

MAN MAN Energy Solutions

MEYER WERFT

RWTH AACHEN
UNIVERSITY

TU Delft

LUND
UNIVERSITY

VTT

Deliverable D8.4 Workbook for public workshop

Short summary: The aim of the deliverable D8.4 Workbook for the public workshop is to describe a planning strategy for workshop preparation and outline all the logical steps that need to be taken or considered.

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Dissemination Level

PU Public

PP Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

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1 Introduction

The aim of this deliverable, D8.4 Workbook for the public workshop, is to provide a comprehensive description of a workbook that will guide the step-by-step preparation of the project final workshop. It serves as a valuable resource for workshop organizers, outlining all the necessary tasks and considerations to ensure a successful event and limiting potential risks. The workbook is designed in the form of a checklist, allowing organizers to easily keep track of their progress in time and ensure that no crucial aspects are overlooked.

While compiling this workbook, the dynamic nature of workshops and the fact that not all points may remain relevant in the future, was taken into account. Being aware that that circumstances can change quickly, it is essential to have a flexible framework that can be adapted to different situations. The workbook provides a holistic view of the workshop preparation process, presenting various perspectives that organizers should consider to ensure a comprehensive and inclusive event.

To ensure the workbook's effectiveness, it has been developed with the input of experienced workshop organizers. Specifically, the insights gained during the organization of the workshop in Lucerne in July 2022 have served as valuable sources for preparing this deliverable. The challenges faced, lessons learned, and best practices observed during that event have all contributed to the refinement and improvement of the workbook.

In order to validate and fine-tune the preparatory steps and timeline outlined in the workbook, the D8.4 will be put to the test during the upcoming preparation of the project's technical workshop in July 2024. This practical implementation will provide an opportunity to assess the effectiveness and practicality of the workbook's guidelines. Any necessary adjustments or updates identified during this process will be promptly incorporated into the workbook to enhance its utility and relevance.

It is important to note that this deliverable was scheduled one year prior to the NAUTILUS project's final conference. As the project progresses and new insights emerge, it is crucial to remain agile and responsive to changing circumstances. Therefore, if any modifications or revisions are deemed necessary for the smooth organisation of the final project conference.

After the submission of D8.4, it was decided that the project conference in 2024 would be coordinated with an already established conference in the relevant field. Following the positive experience of co-organizing the project workshop in Lucerne with The European Fuel Cell Forum (EFCF) organizers, this approach was repeated. Sustainable Shipping Days (SSD) is the novel conference format created in partnership between EFCF and Nautilus specialised on application of cell-based in onboard energy systems and electrolysis technology at ports for fuel supply. The Sustainable Shipping Days SSD 2024 will be held at the Culture and Convention Centre Lucerne (KKL) at July 1-2, 2024 in conjunction with the Fuel Cell, Electrolyser & H2 Technology and Supplier Exhibition.

The overall goal of this deliverable remains the same - to ensure that the workbook remains up-to-date and tailored to the specific needs and objectives of the NAUTILUS project, ultimately contributing to the success of the final conference.

2 The Preparation Process Step-By-Step

2.1 The Early Phase (12-9 Months Before the Event)

During the early phase of preparation, several key considerations need to be addressed:

- Shaping the scope and form of the event
- Identifying the focus and key topics
- Defining the target audience
- Determining the target number of attendees
- Establishing the length of the event
- Deciding whether the event will be onsite only or hybrid
- Determining whether the event will be a self-standing event or a side-event to a conference/fair with project-relevant content
- Assessing the financial sources available for organizing the event
- Considering key aspects for location selection and choosing the date
- Establishing a logical link or tie to a proxy event
- Evaluating geographical and logistical aspects of the chosen location
- Analysing the cost-benefit ratio
- Reviewing the cancellation policy
- Decision on coordination of the event with an already established conference in the relevant field.
- Cooperation with the European Fuel Cell Forum (EFCF, <https://www.efcf.com>)

2.2 The Preparation Phase (9-3 Months Before the Event)

2.2.1 The Event Promo – Getting Attention

During this phase, the focus is on promoting the event to generate interest and awareness:

- Selecting a name for the event and defining a key hashtag – Sustainable Shipping Days (SSD)
- Creating a subsite at EFCF website (<https://www.efcf.com/ssd>) as a landing page with basic information
- Sending out a "save the date" notification via newsletters, micro-newsletters, social media profiles and website
- Distributing placeholders or invitations through partner channels (EFCF channels), including key topic areas, the event's time and location, and a link to the landing page or subpage <https://www.efcf.com/ssd>

2.2.2 The Event Logistics

2.2.2.1 Location for Self-Standing Events – not relevant

For self-standing events, the following steps should be taken:

- Contracting with the location owner and meeting deadlines for pre-payment of services
- Clarifying the cancellation policy
- Ensuring that the organizer has appropriate insurance coverage
- Checking technical prerequisites at the venue, such as a stable WIFI connection, microphones, seating arrangements, cloakroom facilities, and sufficient space for cameras based on the planned seating configuration
- Obtaining photos and plans of the venue and establishing contact with the event manager
- Considering accommodation options within the budget per person and confirming what is included in the price (e.g., breakfast, parking slots) with deadlines for confirming attendee numbers
- Obtaining offers for refreshment packages and establishing a beverage policy, along with a deadline for final confirmation of attendee numbers
- Verifying whether transportation costs are included in the price of accommodation
- Securing additional staff for check-in, either through the hotel or the organizer

Please note that the above steps provide a guideline for the preparation process and should be adapted to suit the specific requirements and circumstances of the event.

2.2.2.2 Location for Side-Events

When organizing a side-event, the following considerations should be taken into account:

- Price, cancellation policy, and responsibilities of the main organizer and NAUTILUS organizers should be defined and codified. Due to the arrangement with the EFCF organisers, logistics of the event (points below) are under responsibility of the EFCF organising team, NAUTILUS takes part in the coordination of the conference scientific content & media support promotion
- Check technical prerequisites at the location, such as a stable WIFI connection, microphones, seating arrangements, cloakroom facilities, and sufficient space for cameras based on the planned seating configuration. Obtain photos, plans, and contact information from the venue.
- Determine what is included in the cooperation package, including accommodation, breakfast, refreshments, lunch, and any additional services such as personnel for conference check-in.
- Consider any central transportation options for the conference and check if free parking slots are available.

2.2.3 The Event Content

The conference organisation teams were created, one for the coordination of the scientific content of the event, the other for event logistic and promotion. These teams consist of EFCF organisers, the NAUTILUS coordinator and his administrative team and consortium members upon need.

During the preparation phase, the event content should be carefully planned:

- Identify and invite key speakers for the event.
- Contact confirmed speakers to obtain their photos and CVs/short bios for event PR purposes.
- Set deadlines for presentations to be submitted to the organizer.
- Ensure the content of the event website is ready, including logistics information and the main topics of the program. Regularly update speaker's information.

2.2.3.1 Definition of Outputs

The event is a hybrid event with two levels of conference fees. Registration is held online and completely managed by EFCF. All the points below are under responsibility of the EFCF:

- Organize an online stream for the event and address any potential technical troubleshooting.
- Secure the necessary materials, including videos from the online sessions, for future PR use.
- Decide on the need for proceedings and determine the ideal form.
- Consider whether photos should be provided in-house or by a professional photographer.
- Determine if an event video is necessary and make arrangements to contract a cameraman or secure relevant material from the online session. Set a deadline for the finalized outcome.

2.3 The Late Phase (3-0 Months Before the Event)

2.3.1 The Event Logistics

During the late phase, specific logistical aspects need to be addressed, under the agreement, these points are under split responsibility:

EFCF organisers responsibility:

- Establish a fixed refreshment/lunch menu based on the expected number of attendees, in line with the cancellation policy.
- Define rules for export control, if applicable, including the extent and timing of controls.
- Ensure that the registration form is active on the website by the specified date, and consider export control and GDPR regulations.
- Central PR materials for the event, such as the design of the project roll-up, lanyards, name badges etc.
- Arrange all necessary for printouts before the event, including the program, presentations, , participant lists for check-in with consent for photos/videos (GDPR), and arrows to the conference room/check-in

NAUTILUS responsibility

Determine if a 3D ship model will be present at the event, and if so, define responsibilities and contacts with DLR Geesthacht. Verify if an official agreement with DLR Geesthacht is required and ensure proper insurance coverage. Consider the size, weight, and logistics of the ship model.

- Print and deliver updated NAUTILUS leaflets
- Determine whether the NAUTILUS roll up is needed, if so, print and delivery to be assured

2.3.2 The Event Content

Shared responsibility of SSD Scientific Board.

Ensure the event content is well-prepared:

- Define the roles of the organizing team and create a key contact list + internal SharePoint where key working documents are stored
- Secure the list of speakers and their presentations.

Responsibility of EFCF organisers:

- Arrange for necessary technical support, such as a photographer and cameraman.
- Ensure additional personnel are secured, including:
 - o Moderator for the event.
 - o Onsite technology helpdesk for troubleshooting issues (WIFI, microphones, etc.)
 - o Contact person for onsite printing in case of any changes to printed materials.
 - o If it's a hybrid event, assign a person responsible for live chat.

2.3.3 The Event Promo – The Call for Action

- Identify key visuals and communication topics – EFCF team responsibility
- Intensify marketing efforts on social media and specialized groups, utilizing micro newsletter format and partner channels - EFCF team responsibility, NAUTILUS support
- Issue a press release through partners' communication channels when the (pre-)final version of the program is available on the web (approximately 4-6 weeks before the event). - EFCF team responsibility, NAUTILUS support
- Promote key speakers by featuring their photos and short bios - EFCF team responsibility, NAUTILUS support
- Present key topics of the event and include a link to the registration page - EFCF team responsibility, NAUTILUS support
- If the NAUTILUS workshop is organized alongside another relevant event:
 - o Follow the main event on social media.
 - o Use their main event hashtag in our communication.
 - o Secure PR link to the main event through NAUTILUS' presentation on their program, website, and social media.

2.4 The Event/Just Before the Event

2.4.1 The Event Logistics

EFCF organisers responsibility:

- Provide transportation information, including details about taxi or public transport options for speakers and a helpdesk contact in case of any unforeseen situations.
- Collect business cards
- Onsite, obtain consent for photographs at the registration desk (GDPR).

2.4.1.1 Location if the event is a side-event

NAUTILUS responsibility:

- Check if any on-site access requires registration or passcodes.
- Verify if there are any restrictions on access to other events at the location for our attendees.

2.4.2 The Event Content

EFCF organisers responsibility:

- Create and distribute questions/topics for discussion to speakers and/or the moderator.
- Define specific roles and responsibilities for the organizing team at the event site.

NAUTILUS responsibility:

- Determine the date and location of the final/end project event and mention it as a save-the-date.

2.4.3 The Event Promo – The Last Call

- Make a final call for registration on social media and in relevant groups - EFCF organisers, NAUTILUS support

2.5 The Post-event (1-2 Months After the Event)

2.5.1 The Event Logistics

NAUTILUS responsibility:

- If a 3D ship model was delivered to the location, ensure its return to DLR.
- Review and settle invoices.

2.5.2 The Event Content

- Prepare a post-event article or press release, ensuring speakers' consent is obtained.

- If applicable, ensure video production is taken care of.
- Store the final version of presentations in the project archive and consider publishing them on the project website (subject to speakers' consent).
- Obtain speakers' consent for the publication of photos, especially if not collected on-site.
- Obtain speakers' consent for the publication of relevant videos.
- If applicable, obtain speakers' consent for the publication of proceedings.

2.5.3 The Event Promo – Content and the Future Event

- Extend gratitude to speakers and attendees.
- Publish approved materials on the web or SharePoint.
- Promote the published materials.
- Include the materials in micro newsletters or newsletters.
- Announce the date and location of the final/end project event as a save-the-date.

3 To-be-archived Materials

The list of materials to be archived in the project includes:

- Legal documents (contracts)
- The participant list – on site
- Presentations of speakers
- Photographs
- Video (if relevant)
- Final version of PR materials (if relevant)
- Invoices

4 The Timeline

5 The Preparation Follow-up

5.1 For Internal Communication

For internal communication throughout the preparation process, the standard project communication tools, which involves using internal LOGs in SharePoint and SharePoint with EFCF team (instead of Excel) will be utilized. This internal site includes a comprehensive list of all the relevant tasks mentioned earlier with clear link of each task to its responsibility and deadline. This internal site provides a handy space for tracking, monitoring and archiving all conference related materials. Furthermore, conference calls will be initiated as needed to ensure effective communication and collaboration among team members, both on the side of the content side and logistics & promotion side. These calls will serve as a platform for discussing important matters, addressing any questions or concerns, and making necessary decisions in a timely manner.

5.2 For External Communication

The content for external communication will be drafted in cooperation with EFCF. On the NAUTILUS side, the LOG of release for PR and communication materials will be utilized. This LOG serves as a centralized storage point for materials intended for external communication. These materials will be shared with project partners for their valuable input and feedback. To ensure a collaborative and transparent process, the materials will be made available for partner comments for a duration of four days. Only after this feedback period, the materials shall be published on the project website and shared on our social media platforms.

6 Summary

In conclusion, the preparation process for the workshop outlined in the Conference workbook involves various important steps and considerations. (i) The early phase focuses on shaping the scope and format of the event, defining the target audience, and selecting the location and collaboration setup. (ii) The preparation phase involves event promotion, logistics planning, and defining the event content and outputs. (iii) The late phase involves finalizing logistics, ensuring event content readiness, and intensifying event promotion. (iv) After the event, post-event activities include logistic wrap-up, content publication, and continued promotion. Throughout the process, internal communication is facilitated through project communication tools, and external communication is managed through a designated LOG of Release and dedicated SharePoint site. By following these steps and utilizing effective communication channels, the workshop preparation can be organized smoothly and efficiently.